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Research Article

**A NEW ANALYTICAL RP-HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT
AND VALIDATION FOR THE ANALYSIS OF
ACENOCOUMAROL (NICOUMALONE) IN API FORM AND
MARKETED PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORMS****Sunitha^{1*}, G. Deepika², Vijaya Kuchana³, Pasupuleti Sunitha⁴, G. Kalyani⁵**^{1*}Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet (V), Balapur (M), Ranga Reddy (Dist), Hyderabad – 500097, Telangana²Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Assistant Professor, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet (V), Balapur (M), Ranga Reddy (Dist), Hyderabad – 500097, Telangana³Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Principal and Professor, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet (V), Balapur (M), Ranga Reddy (Dist), Hyderabad – 500097, Telangana⁴Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Associate Professor, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet (V), Balapur (M), Ranga Reddy (Dist), Hyderabad – 500097, Telangana⁵Department of Pharmaceutical Chemistry, Associate Professor, Teegala Krishna Reddy College of Pharmacy, Medbowli, Meerpet (V), Balapur (M), Ranga Reddy (Dist), Hyderabad – 500097, Telangana**Abstract:**

A new, simple, rapid, precise, accurate and reproducible RP-HPLC method for estimation of Nicoumalone in bulk form and marketed formulation. Separation of Nicoumalone was successfully achieved on a Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. column in an isocratic mode of separation utilizing Methanol : Phosphate buffer (0.02M, pH-3.6) in the ratio of 45:55% v/v at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and the detection was carried out at 255nm. The method was validated according to ICH guidelines for linearity, sensitivity, accuracy, precision, specificity and robustness. The response was found to be linear in the drug concentration range of 12-28mcg/mL for Nicoumalone. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9995 for Nicoumalone. The LOD and LOQ for Nicoumalone were found to be 5.004 μ g/mL and 15.164 μ g/mL respectively. The proposed method was found to be good percentage recovery for Nicoumalone, which indicates that the proposed method is highly accurate. The specificity of the method shows good correlation between retention times of standard solution with the sample solution. Therefore, the proposed method specifically determines the analyte in the sample without interference from excipients of pharmaceutical dosage forms.

Keywords: Nicoumalone, RP-HPLC, Accuracy, Precision, Robustness, ICH Guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION:

Acenocoumarol is an anticoagulant drug used in the prevention of thromboembolic diseases in infarction and transient ischemic attacks, as well as management of deep vein thrombosis and myocardial infarction. Acenocoumarol is a hydroxycoumarin that is warfarin in which the hydrogen at position 4 of the phenyl substituent is replaced by a nitro group. It has a role as an anticoagulant and an EC 1.6.5.2 [NAD (P) H dehydrogenase (Quinone)] inhibitor¹. It is a C-nitro compound, a hydroxycoumarin and a methyl ketone. For the treatment and prevention of thromboembolic diseases. More specifically, it is

indicated for the prevention of cerebral embolism, deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary embolism, thromboembolism in infarction and transient ischemic attacks. It is used for the treatment of deep vein thrombosis and myocardial infarction². Nicoumalone is used to prevent and treat various types of thromboembolic diseases (blood clots inside blood vessels), including deep vein thrombosis (blood clots in leg veins) and pulmonary embolism (blood clots in the lung). The IUPAC Name of Nicoumalone is 4-hydroxy-3-[1-(4-nitrophenyl)-3-oxobutyl] chromen-2-one³. The Chemical Structure of Nicoumalone is as following

Fig-1: Chemical Structure of Nicoumalone

After performing an extensive literature review³¹⁻³², an attempt was made to develop a smooth plain sailing, unambiguous, valid, speedy, and decisive strategy for estimating Nicoumalone in bulk form and marketed pharmaceutical dosage form by using RP-HPLC.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Table-1: Instruments used**

S.No.	Instruments and Glass wares	Model
1	HPLC	WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.
2	pH meter	Lab India
3	Weighing machine	Sartorius
4	Volumetric flasks	Borosil
5	Pipettes and Burettes	Borosil
6	Beakers	Borosil
7	Digital ultra sonicator	Labman

Table-2: Chemicals used

S.No.	Chemical	Brand names
1	Nicoumalone	Synpharma Research Lab, Hyderabad
2	Water and Methanol for HPLC	LICHROSOLV (MERCK)
3	Acetonitrile for HPLC	Merck
4	Ethanol	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
5	DMSO	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
6	DMF	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
7	Orthophosphoric Acid	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai

HPLC METHOD DEVELOPMENT:

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Twenty capsules were taken and the average weight was calculated as per the method prescribed in I.P. The weighed tablets were finally powdered and triturated well. A quantity of powder of Nicoumalone equivalent to 10mg were transferred to clean and dry 10 ml volumetric flask and 7 ml of HPLC grade methanol was added and the resulting solution was sonicated for 15 minutes. Make up the volume up to 10 ml with same solvent. Then 1 ml of the above solution was diluted to 10 ml with HPLC grade methanol. One ml (0.1 ml) of the prepared stock solution diluted to 10 ml and was filtered through membrane filter (0.45 μ m) and finally sonicated to degas.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions⁴ and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines¹³⁻¹⁴.

Mobile Phase Optimization:

Initially the mobile phase⁵ tried was Methanol and Methanol: Water with varying proportions. Finally, the mobile phase was optimized to Methanol and Phosphate buffer (0.02M, pH-3.6) in proportion 45:55% v/v.

Optimization of Column:

The method was performed with various C18 columns like, X- bridge column, Xterra, and C18

column. Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. was found to be ideal as it gave good peak shape and resolution at 1.0ml/min flow.

Preparation of Buffer and Mobile Phase:

Preparation of Potassium Dihydrogen Phosphate (KH₂PO₄) Buffer (0.02M) (pH-3.6):

Dissolve 2.72172g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate in 1000 ml HPLC water and adjust the pH 3.6 with diluted orthophosphoric acid. Filter and sonicate the solution by vacuum filtration⁶ and ultra-sonication.

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

Accurately measured 450 ml (45%) of Methanol and 550 ml of Phosphate buffer (55%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultra sonicator for 15 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

METHOD VALIDATION PARAMETERS

System Suitability

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for five times and measured the area for all five injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of five replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Specificity:

Preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of Sample Solution:

Weight 10 mg equivalent weight of Nicoumalone sample into a 10mL clean dry volumetric flask and add about 7mL of Diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent.

Further pipette 0.1ml of Nicoumalone above stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluent.

Procedure:

Inject the three replicate injections of standard and sample solutions and calculate the assay⁷ by using formula:

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area} \times \text{Weight of standard} \times \text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Purity} \times \text{Weight of tablet} \times \text{Standard area} \times \text{Dilution of standard} \times \text{Weight of sample}} \times 100$$

Linearity and Range:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Preparation of Level – I (12ppm of Nicoumalone):

Take 0.12ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – II (16ppm of Nicoumalone):

Take 0.16ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – III (20ppm of Nicoumalone):

Take 0.2ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – IV (24ppm of Nicoumalone):

Take 0.24ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Preparation of Level – V (28ppm of Nicoumalone):

Take 0.28ml of stock solution in to 10ml of volumetric flask and make up the volume up to mark with diluents and sonicate the solution for bubble entrapment using ultrasonicator.

Procedure:

Inject each level into the chromatographic system and measure the peak area.

Plot a graph of peak area versus concentration (on X-axis concentration and on Y-axis Peak area) and calculate the correlation coefficient.

Precision

Repeatability

Preparation of Nicoumalone Product Solution for Precision:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Intermediate Precision:

To evaluate the intermediate precision (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:

Analyst 1:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Analyst 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Accuracy:

For Preparation of 80% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.08ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 100% Standard Stock Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

For Preparation of 120% Standard Stock

Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.12ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Procedure:

Inject the Three replicate injections of individual concentrations (80%, 100%, 120%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Nicoumalone and calculate the individual recovery⁸ and mean recovery values.

Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification (LOD & LOQ):

Preparation of 5.004µg/ml Solution (For LOD):

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.05004ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Preparation of 15.164µg/ml Solution (For LOQ):

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.15164ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Robustness:

The analysis was performed in different conditions to find the variability of test results. The following conditions are checked for variation of results. .

For Preparation of Standard Solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Nicoumalone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7mL of Diluents and sonicate to dissolve it completely and make volume up to the mark with the same solvent. (Stock solution)

Further pipette 0.1ml of the above Nicoumalone stock solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with diluents.

Effect of Variation of Flow Conditions:

The sample was analyzed at 0.9 ml/min and 1.1 ml/min instead of 1ml/min, remaining conditions are same. 20µl of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Effect of Variation of Mobile Phase Organic Composition:

The sample was analyzed by variation of mobile phase i.e. Methanol: Phosphate Buffer was taken in the ratio and 50:50, 40:60 instead (45:55), remaining conditions are same. 20µl of the above sample was injected and chromatograms were recorded.

Forced Degradation Studies

The purpose of stability testing⁹⁻¹² is to provide evidence on how the quality of a drug substance or drug product varies with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, and light, and to establish a re-test period for the drug substance or a shelf life for the drug.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Selection of Wavelength:

The detection wavelength was selected by dissolving the drug in mobile phase to get a concentration of 10µg/ml for individual and mixed standards. The resulting solution was scanned in U.V range from 200-400nm. The UV spectrum¹⁵ of Nicoumalone was obtained and the Nicoumalone showed absorbance's maxima at 255nm. The UV spectra of drug are follows:

Fig-2: UV Spectrum of Nicoumalone (255nm)

Observation: While scanning the Nicoumalone solution we observed the maxima at 255nm. The UV spectrum has been recorded on T60-LAB INDIA make UV – Vis spectrophotometer model UV-2450.

Method Development

Several concurrent trails developed the proposed method to establish the preferred chromatographic conditions, which would be helpful to conduct a complete validation study. The optimal conditions considered for mobile phase were 45:55% v/v ratio of Methanol and 0.02M potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate buffer at pH 3.6 and Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C18, 5µm, 15cmx4.6mm i.d.

Column¹⁶ were used, which gave a sharp symmetric peak, minimum tailing factor with short run time for Nicoumalone at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and detection wavelength 255 nm was optimized. Sample of 20 μ L was injected in to

Optimized Chromatographic Method:

HPLC System¹⁷ and the different optimization of chromatographic parameters is depicted in Table 3. The retention time for Nicoumalone was found to be 3.254 minutes (Figure 3).

Table-3: Optimized Chromatographic Conditions

Mobile phase	Methanol : Phosphate buffer (0.02M, pH-3.6) = 45:55 v/v
Column	Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C ₁₈ , 5 μ m, 15cmx4.6mm i.d.
Column Temperature	Ambient
Detection Wavelength	255 nm
Flow rate	1.0 ml/ min.
Run time	07 min.
Temperature of Auto sampler	Ambient
Diluent	Mobile Phase
Injection Volume	20 μ l
Type of Elution	Isocratic

Fig-3: Optimized Chromatographic Condition

Conclusion: This trial shows proper plate count, peak and baseline in the chromatogram. It's Pass the all system suitability parameters. So, it's optimized chromatogram.

Validation of Analytical Method

System Suitability: System suitability testing is an integral part of many analytical procedures. The tests are based on the concept that the equipment, electronics, analytical operations and samples to be analyzed constitute an integral system that can be evaluated as such. Following system suitability test parameters¹⁸ were established. The data are shown in Table-4 & 5.

Table-4: Data of System Suitability Test

S.No.	Injection No.	RT	Area	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Injection 1	3.253	284568	7368	1.26
2	Injection 2	3.254	285684	7295	1.25
3	Injection 3	3.215	283659	7346	1.27
4	Injection 4	3.297	284754	7394	1.29
5	Injection 5	3.253	283695	7425	1.25
6	Injection 6	3.213	284578	7385	1.27
Mean			284489.7	7368.833	1.265
S.D			752.5617		
%RSD			0.26453		

Table-5: System Suitability Results for Nicoumalone (Flow rate)

S.No.	Parameter	Limit	Result
1	Asymmetry	$T \leq 2$	Nicoumalone = 0.12
2	Theoretical plate	$N > 2000$	Nicoumalone = 7258
3	Tailing Factor	$(Tf) < 2$	Nicoumalone = 1.25

Specificity:

Specificity¹⁹ can be determined by comparing the chromatograms obtained from the drugs with the chromatogram obtained from the blank solution. Blank solution was prepared by mixing the excipients in the mobile phase without drug. Drug solutions were prepared individually and the sample containing three drugs was also prepared. Now these mixtures were filtered by passing through 0.45 μ membrane filter before the analysis. In this observation no excipient peaks were obtained near the drug in the study run time. This indicates that the proposed method was specific. The chromatograms representing the peaks of blank, Nicoumalone and the sample containing the three drugs were shown in following figures respectively.

Observation: In this test method blank, standard solutions were analyzed individually to examine the interference. The above chromatograms show that the active ingredient was well separated from blank and their excipients and there was no interference of blank with the principal peak. Hence the method is specific.

Linearity: To evaluate the linearity²⁰, serial dilution of analyte were prepared from the stock solution was diluted with mobile phase to get a series of concentration ranging from 0-28 μ g/ml for Nicoumalone. The prepared solutions were filtered through Whatman filter paper (No.41). From these solutions, 20 μ l injections of each concentration were injected into the HPLC system and chromatographed under the optimized conditions. Calibration curve²¹ was constructed by plotting the mean peak area (Y-axis) against the concentration (X-axis).

Plotting of Calibration Graphs: The resultant areas of linearity peaks are plotted against Concentration.

Fig-4: Standard Curve for Nicoumalone

Observation: Linearity range²² was found to be 0-28 μ g/ml for Nicoumalone. The correlation coefficient was found to be 0.9995, the slope was found to be 55283 and intercept was found to be 12871 for Nicoumalone.

Table-6: Linearity Readings for Nicoumalone

CONC.(μ g/ml)	MEAN AUC (n=6)
0	0
12	690316
16	910621
20	1121057
24	1328903
28	1554666

Linearity Plot: The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Nicoumalone is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 55283$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 12871$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.9995$$

Acceptance/Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 12871. These values meet the validation criteria.

Accuracy:

Inject the three replicate injections of individual concentrations (80%, 100%, 120%) were made under the optimized conditions. Recorded the chromatograms and measured the peak responses. Calculate the Amount found and Amount added for Nicoumalone and calculate the individual recovery and mean recovery values²³. Accuracy at different concentrations (80%, 100%, and 120%) was prepared and the % recovery was calculated.

Table-7: Accuracy Results of Nicoumalone

Sample ID	Concentration (µg/ml)			%Recovery of Pure drug	Statistical Analysis
	Conc. Found	Conc. Recovered	Peak Area		
S ₁ : 80 %	8	8.064107	458679	99.867	Mean= 100.4113% S.D. = 0.473694346 % R.S.D.= 0.471753
S ₂ : 80 %	8	7.843532	446485	100.637	
S ₃ : 80 %	8	8.19449	465887	100.73	
S ₄ : 100 %	10	9.892661	559767	99.41	Mean= 100.6646667% S.D. = 1.166369295 R.S.D.= 1.158667
S ₅ : 100 %	10	9.978655	564521	100.868	
S ₆ : 100 %	10	10.19623	576549	101.716	
S ₇ : 120 %	12	11.85907	668476	99.878	Mean= 100.4637% S.D. = 0.51154309 % R.S.D. = 0.509181
S ₈ : 120 %	12	12.16785	685546	100.69	
S ₉ : 120 %	12	12.18644	686574	100.823	

Observation: The mean recoveries were found to be 100.411, 100.664 and 100.463% for Nicoumalone. The limit for mean % recovery is 98-102% and as both the values are within the limit, hence it can be said that the proposed method was accurate.

Precision: The precision²⁴ of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug Nicoumalone. The percent relative standard deviations were calculated for Nicoumalone are presented in the Table-8.

i) Repeatability

Obtained Six (6) replicates of 100% accuracy solution as per experimental conditions. Recorded the peak areas and calculated % RSD.

Table-8: Repeatability Results of Nicoumalone

HPLC Injection Replicates	AUC for Nicoumalone
Replicate – 1	285479
Replicate – 2	284571
Replicate – 3	286954
Replicate – 4	283261
Replicate – 5	285964
Replicate – 6	284259
Average	285081.3
Standard Deviation	1318.666
% RSD	0.462558

Observation: The repeatability study which was conducted on the solution having the concentration of about 20µg/ml for Nicoumalone (n=6) showed a RSD of 0.462558% for Nicoumalone. It was concluded that the analytical technique showed good repeatability.

ii) Intermediate Precision / Ruggedness

To evaluate the intermediate precision²⁵ (also known as Ruggedness) of the method, Precision was performed on different days by maintaining same conditions.

Procedure:

Analyst 1: The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits.

Analyst 2:

The standard solution was injected for six times and measured the area for all six injections in HPLC. The %RSD for the area of six replicate injections was found to be within the specified limits²⁹⁻³⁰.

Intra Day (Day-1)/Analyst-1:

Table-9: Results of Ruggedness for Nicoumalone (Analyst-1)

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Peak Area	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Nicoumalone	3.253	284568	7368	1.26
2	Nicoumalone	3.254	285684	7295	1.25
3	Nicoumalone	3.215	283659	7346	1.27
4	Nicoumalone	3.204	286598	7457	1.22
5	Nicoumalone	3.202	287965	7635	1.29
6	Nicoumalone	3.297	285698	7459	1.28
Mean			285695.3		
Std. Dev.			1508.898		
% RSD			0.528149		

Inter Day (Day -2)/Analyst-2)

Table-10: Results of Ruggedness for Nicoumalone (Analyst-2)

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Peak Area	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
1	Nicoumalone	3.297	294754	7394	1.29
2	Nicoumalone	3.253	293695	7425	1.25
3	Nicoumalone	3.213	294578	7385	1.27
4	Nicoumalone	3.297	296534	7584	1.23
5	Nicoumalone	3.210	296571	7745	1.24
6	Nicoumalone	3.254	298698	7658	1.25
Mean			295805		
Std. Dev.			1819.334		
% RSD			0.615045		

Robustness: Robustness²⁶ is defined as the capacity of that method to be unaffected by even small deliberate changes that occur in the method parameters. The evaluation of robustness of a method is done by varying the chromatographic parameters such as pH, temperature, flow rate, mobile phase proportions change, ionic strength etc., and determining any possible effect on the results obtained by that method.

Table-11: Result of Method Robustness Test for Nicoumalone

Parameter used for Sample Analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	283261	3.254	7258	1.25
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	315864	3.297	7569	1.29
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	298542	3.212	7841	1.41
Less organic phase	279856	3.253	7965	1.27
More organic phase	306985	3.215	7458	1.28

LOD: The limit of detection (LOD) is the lowest concentration of analyte in a sample which can be detected, but not quantitated. LOD²⁷ is a limit test that specifies whether an analyte is above or below a certain value. Signal-to-noise ratio of three-to-one is used to determine LOD.

$$L.O.D. = 3.3 (SD/S).$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Table-12: Results of LOD

	LOD
SD of Intercept	19518.16286
Slope	55283

Observation: The LOD was found to be 1.165µg/ml for Nicoumalone.

LOQ: The Limit of Quantitation (LOQ) is defined as the lowest concentration of an analyte in a sample that can be determined with acceptable precision and accuracy under the stated operational conditions of the method. Signal-to-noise ratio of ten-to-one is used to determine LOQ²⁸.

$$L.O.Q. = 10 (SD/S)$$

Where, SD = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Table-13: Results of LOQ

	LOQ
SD of Intercept	19518.16286
Slope	55283

Observation: The LOQ was found to be 3.53µg/ml for Nicoumalone.

Assay of Pharmaceutical Dosage form

Twenty tablets/Capsules were taken and the I.P. method was followed to determine the average weight. Finally the weighed tablets are powdered and triturated well by using mortar and pestle. A quantity of powder which is equivalent to the 100mg of drugs were transferred to a clean and dry 100ml of volumetric flask and add 70 ml of mobile phase and the resulted solution was sonicated for 15 minutes by using ultra sonicator, Then the final volume was make up to the mark with the mobile phase. The final solution was filtered through a selected membrane filter (0.45 µm) and in order to sonicate to degas the mobile phase (Solvent system). From this above stock arrangement (1 ml) was exchanged to five distinctive 10 ml volumetric flagons and volume was made up to 10 ml with same dissolvable framework (Mobile stage).

The readied arrangements were infused in five repeats into the HPLC framework and the perceptions were recorded.

A duplicate injection (Blank Solution) of the standard arrangement likewise infused into the HPLC framework and the chromatograms and peak zones were recorded and figured.

ASSAY:

Assay % =

$$\frac{AT}{AS} \times \frac{WS}{DS} \times \frac{DT}{WT} \times \frac{P}{100} \times \text{Avg. Wt} = \text{mg/tab}$$

Where:

AT = Peak Area of drug obtained with test preparation

AS = Peak Area of drug obtained with standard preparation

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of sample taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard solution

DT = Dilution of sample solution

P = Percentage purity of working standard

The assay was performed as explained in the previous chapter. The results which are obtained are following:

Table-14: Recovery Data for estimation Nicoumalone in Molflu Capsule

Brand Name of Nicoumalone	Labelled amount of Drug (mg)	Amount (mg) found by the proposed method (n=3)	Assay %
Nicomalom 1mg Tablet (Steris Healthcare Pvt Ltd)	1mg	0.947mg	99.648%

Result & Discussion: The amount of drug in Molflu Capsule was found to be 199.695 (± 0.789) mg/tab for Nicoumalone & % Purity²⁹ was 99.598 (± 0.695) %.

Forced Degradation Studies

Following protocol was strictly adhered to for forced degradation of Nicoumalone Active Pharmaceutical Ingredient (API). The API (Nicoumalone) was subjected to keep in some stress conditions in various ways to observe the rate and extent of degradation that is likely to occur in the course of storage and/or after administration to body. It is one type of accelerated stability studies of the drugs that is used to help us to determining the total fate of the drug that is likely to happen after long time storage, within a very short time as

compare to the real time or long term stability testing. The different types of forced degradation pathways/studies are studied here are acid hydrolysis, basic hydrolysis, thermal degradation and oxidative degradation.

The results of the forced degradation studies³⁰ indicated the specificity of the developed method that has been developed. Nicoumalone were stable only in acidic, thermal and basic stress conditions. The results of stability studies are given in the following Table-15.

Table-15: Results of Force Degradation Studies of Nicoumalone API

Stress Condition	Time (hours)	Assay of active substance	Assay of degraded products	Mass Balance (%)
Acid Hydrolysis (0.1N HCl)	24Hrs.	91.326	8.674	100.00
Basic Hydrolysis (0.1N NaOH)	24Hrs.	83.215	16.785	100.00
Thermal Degradation (60 °C)	24Hrs.	90.311	9.689	100.00
UV (254nm)	24Hrs.	81.322	18.678	100.00
3% Hydrogen Peroxide	24Hrs.	73.514	26.486	100.00

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for analysis of Nicoumalone, different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are presented in previous chapters. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution. In case of RP-HPLC various columns are available, but here Develosil ODS HG-5 RP C₁₈, 5µm, 15cmx4.6mm i.d. column was preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good. Detection wavelength was selected after scanning the standard solution of drug over 200 to 400nm. From the U.V spectrum of Nicoumalone it is evident that most of the HPLC work can be accomplished in the wavelength range of 255 nm conveniently. Further, a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min & an injection volume of 20µl were found to be the best analysis. The result shows the developed method is yet another suitable method for assay which can help in the analysis of Nicoumalone in different formulations.

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